

Empowering the Future of Semiconductor Innovation: Unveiling IHP's Pioneering Skills Development in Microelectronics

Best practice category **Skills**

Stakeholder group **Research and academia**

Value chain position **R&D**

General Information

The IHP - Leibniz Institute for High Performance Microelectronics in Frankfurt (Oder), Germany is a non-university research establishment institutionally funded by the German federal and state governments that is one of the world's leading research institutions in the field of silicon/germanium electronics.

The institute has a pilot line that manufactures circuits using its high-performance SiGe BiCMOS technologies. Through its research and manufacturing services, IHP contributes significantly to the innovative strength of Germany and Europe, especially in the field of ultrahigh-frequency electronics. The institute's research results are applied in socially important areas such as semiconductor manufacturing, wireless and power broadband communications, health, space, Industry 4.0 or Agriculture 4.0 and mobility.

IHP is highlighted here for providing a Best Practice in the Skills category due to its establishment of Joint Labs which strengthen the ties between the research and academic communities and help to foster young talent. Moreover, IHP offers internship placements, summer schools, a fellowship programme and Young Talent Awards that bring education of the future microelectronics workforce to the fore.

Activities and best practices

IHP has established nine Joint Labs, which focus on bridging the gap between research and universities. As part of the Joint Labs, scientists teach courses, conduct research together with the students, in addition to supervising and assessing their research and academic work on undergraduate and postgraduate levels. IHP uses the Joint Labs to establish contacts with young and skilled students to offer them a springboard to join the institute. Research topics tackled at each university are strategically aligned. Contacts which have established as part of the Joint Labs have significantly helped to find qualified scientists for IHP.

IHP cooperates with German universities across 4 cities, as well as the universities in Poland (Zielona Góra), in Italy (Rome) and Turkey (Sabanci). Below, we provide highlights from the research areas and projects that IHP and the partner universities are involved in:

- At Universität Potsdam (Potsdam), the Joint Lab work focuses on wireless systems and sensor networks, with parallel systems and embedded SoC design applications for the Internet of Things (IoT), in addition to developing solutions for increased reliability, safety and compliance. The partners are working on the development of a reliable Ethernet controller for space applications (SEPHY), prototyping computer automation design (CAD) tools for innovative space applications (PISA), as well as developing a European rad-hard 16Mbit MCM SRAM for space applications (EuroSRAM4Space). Moreover, they are collaborating on the development of an adaptive processing platform for sensor data in automated driving (EMPHASED).

- At [BTU Cottbus-Senftenberg \(Cottbus\)](#), the Joint Lab focuses on the dependability and security of distributed computer systems which are used for control and signal processing in real-world environments, such as applications of smart power grids, flight safety control, vehicle control, medical applications and environmental monitoring. Projects done in collaboration with IHP include an SME digital competence centre ([Mittelstand 4.0-Kompetenzzentrum Cottbus](#)), as well as the development of a multi-partner AI platform for critical infrastructure ([KISS-KI](#)) and the development of microsensors in collaboration with local SMEs.
- At the [Technische Universität Berlin \(TUB\)](#), IHP set up two joint labs. At the Bioelectronics department, the Joint Lab's work focuses on the integration of electronic systems in biological environments by pursuing Lab-on-Chip (LoC) solutions. At the Silicon Photonics Joint Lab, the research is geared towards basic device development, device integration and novel photonic-electronic system-on-chip (SoC) demonstrations. The project [BMBF-PEARLS](#) utilises silicon photonics to develop a high-bit-rate, chip-integrated optical transmission technology.
- At the [Sabanci University \(Turkey\)](#), the Joint Virtual Lab focuses on the exploration and development of mm-wave integrated circuits. In particular, the research areas include technology modules development on BiCMOS process for "More-than-Moore" research path, micro- and nano-electronic devices, micro-electro and nano-electro mechanical systems (MEMS-NEMS), heterogeneous and 3D packaging technologies for radio frequencies (RF) and mm-wave circuits, microfluidic technologies for lab-on-chip bio-sensing applications, as well as circuit design for RF, mm-wave and THz applications.
- At the [University of Zielona Góra \(Poland\)](#), the Joint Lab investigates practical approaches to distributed measurement systems, which include the wireless sensor network, IoT or Cyber Physical Systems (CPS). The projects focus on energy management in the intelligent energy grid and improvement of network efficiency ([SmartGrid Platform](#), [ebalance plus](#)), flood protection measures for the population in Słubice and Frankfurt an der Oder ([SmartRiver](#)), development of an automated and energy self-sufficient measuring station for monitoring biodiversity ([AMMOD](#)), as well as developing space applications ([SpaceRegion](#)).
- The cooperation with the University Roma Tre focuses on basic research on the development and engineering of group-IV semiconductor SiGeSn materials and graphene towards the realisation of silicon-based devices operating in the NIR-FIR ranges, as well as towards the realisation of innovative microelectronic devices such as quantum bits and spintronic devices. Additionally, innovative devices enabling new functions of the "in-silicon" technological platform, such as biomolecule sensing, tissue engineering, regenerative medicine, drug delivery, diagnostic procedures are under development.

As of 2023, the staff of IHP's Joint Labs participated in the supervision and assessment of multiple Bachelor and Master theses, offered over 20 modules, courses and lectures, in addition to overseeing over 70 academic publications. The IHP also offers paid [internships](#) and an annual [summer school](#) for students. For outstanding Master theses written in one of IHP research areas, students can gain a monetary prize with the [Young Talent Award](#). Finally, IHP is a partner in several fellowship programmes ([Erasmus+](#), [Scholarship programme of the German economy](#) and [DAAD RISE](#)).

Challenges addressed with this practice

By establishing Joint Labs across universities in Germany, Poland, Italy and Turkey, the IHP significantly contributes to the closing of the skills gap in the semiconductor sector. With its research-academia collaborations, the IHP has been empowering the next generation of chip designers and engineers in Europe and beyond. Moreover, IHP aligns its research outputs with the industry's needs by providing specialised training and hands-on experience to students and researchers, as well as focusing on real-world applications. This practical approach bridges the gap between theoretical knowledge and the actual demands of the semiconductor field.

Finally, the research conducted in areas like hybrid photonics or lab-on-chip technologies fosters leading-edge innovation in semiconductor device development. Combined with the in-house internship programs and initiatives like the Young Talent Awards, the IHP is equipping young researchers and academics with the knowledge and skills necessary for addressing the evolving challenges of the semiconductor industry.